

Kinetics of Oxidation Reaction of Vanadium(V) with D-sorbitol in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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The kinetics of oxidation reaction is studied in presence of excess of substrate and acid concentrations and by estimating unreacted oxidant titrimetrically. The observed pseudo first order rate constant k_{obs} (sec^{-1}) is found to increase with [D-sorbitol], $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2$ $[\text{HSO}_4^-]^2$, ionic strength and with the percentage composition of acetic acid in the binary mixture of acetic acid water. However, the k_{obs} is not affected by change in $[\text{H}^+]$ at constant $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$. The oxidation product is glucose and when the oxidant is in excess, formic acid is obtained as end product. The suitable mechanistic steps involving the formation of free radical are proposed and thermodynamic parameters are reported.

THE oxidation kinetics of polyhydroxy compounds like diols, carbohydrates particularly mono-saccharides have been studied with various metal ion oxidants including Vanadium(V)¹⁻⁴. It, however, seems that hexitols have received little attention. The oxidation of hexitol with Ce(IV)⁵ and Co(III)⁶ have been reported earlier. The kinetics of oxidation reaction of Vanadium(V) with D-sorbitol is reported in this communication.

Experimental

Experimental details and the method employed for kinetic study are the same as reported earlier⁴.

Results

(i) [Vanadium(V)] Dependence: The disappearance of Vanadium(V) with time followed the first order kinetics uniformly when the substrate and acid concentrations are in excess. The pseudo first order rate constants k_{obs} at different Vanadium(V) concentration is reported in Table 1.

(ii) [D-Sorbitol] Dependence: k_{obs} has been found to increase with D-sorbitol, but the order with respect to substrate is fractional (Table 1).

TABLE 1—THE DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [VANADIUM(V)] AND [D-SORBITOL]

[H ₂ SO ₄]=1.90M Temp=70°		
[Vanadium(V)] × 10 ³ M	[D-sorbitol] × 10M	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
12.0	1.3	1.66
10.5	1.3	1.31
9.0	1.3	1.48
7.5	1.3	1.20
6.0	1.3	0.96
6.0	2.6	2.02
6.0	4.0	2.75
6.0	5.3	3.43
6.0	6.6	3.81

(iii) [H₂SO₄] Dependence:

k_{obs} has been found to increase with square of the concentration of sulphuric acid (Table 2). A plot of log k_o against log [H₂SO₄] can be drawn. The slope is obtained as 2.0.

TABLE 2—THE DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [H₂SO₄]
[Vanadium(V)]=6.0 × 10⁻³M [D-sorbitol]=1.3 × 10⁻¹M
Temp=70°

[H ₂ SO ₄]M	1.2	2.3	3.4	4.5	5.6
k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	0.96	1.70	3.48	5.47	8.93

(iv) [H⁺] and [HSO₄⁻] Dependence:

The rate of oxidation reaction (k_{obs} sec⁻¹) has been found at different [H⁺] by keeping [HSO₄⁻] constant by NaHSO₄ solution, and at different [HSO₄⁻] at constant [H⁺]. k_{obs} is not much affected by [H⁺] but vary with [HSO₄⁻]² (Table 3).

TABLE 3—THE DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [H⁺] AND [HSO₄⁻]

[Vanadium(V)]=6.0 × 10⁻³M [D sorbitol]=1.3 × 10⁻¹M
Temp=70°

[H ⁺]M	[HSO ₄ ⁻] M	k_{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.1	2.0	3.17
0.5	2.0	3.53
1.0	2.0	2.28
1.5	2.0	3.83
2.0	2.0	2.17
1.2	1.2	0.96
1.2	1.4	1.23
1.2	1.7	2.12
1.2	2.2	3.01
1.2	3.2	4.66

(v) % Composition of Acetic Acid-Water Dependence:

k_{obs} increases rapidly on changing the % composition of acetic acid in the binary mixture of acetic acid-water (Table 4).

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When V(V) is in excess.

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